

Demo: SDR-based Implementation of Adaptive OFDM LiFi System

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Abstract—With its high data rates and electromagnetic interference-free operation capability, visible light communication (VLC), also known as LiFi, has emerged as a potential candidate for 6G and beyond networks. In this demo, we present an experimental demonstration of a LiFi system on a software-defined platform. The physical layer of the demo system builds upon direct current biased optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM) and supports adaptive transmission with different modulation schemes/levels including BPSK, 4-QAM, 8-PSK, 16-QAM and 64-QAM. For switching between different modulation schemes, a feedback link with on/off keying modulation is used to send channel state information (CSI) to the OFDM transmitter. Based on the CSI, the OFDM transmitter adapts its next transmission by selecting a modulation scheme which maximizes the spectral efficiency while satisfying a predefined error performance target of 3.8×10^{-3} .

Index Terms—Software Defined Radio, USRP, LiFi, VLC, OFDM, 6G, Spectral Efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

With its high data rates and electromagnetic interference-free operation capability, visible light communication (VLC) has emerged as a potential candidate for 6G and beyond networks. VLC, also known as LiFi, leverages existing lighting infrastructure for both illumination and data transmission by modulating LEDs at a very high frequency unnoticeable to the human eye. One of the key challenges associated with VLC is the bandwidth limitation associated with commercial white LEDs, which behave as first order low-pass filters [1], [2]. Multicarrier modulation schemes such as orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) are commonly employed to overcome the distortion imposed by bandwidth limitation. Furthermore, the optical wireless channel varies with time due to device or user mobility in addition to environmental conditions, and this can impair the performance of the LiFi system. Adaptive transmission allows the switching between different modulation sizes and is critical to satisfy the system performance requirements in terms of bit error rate, spectral efficiency and power efficiency.

In this demo, we present an adaptive LiFi system on a software-defined platform with the capability of switching between different modulations based on the channel state

information. For this purpose, we use modified Ettus USRP x310 [3] platforms where the RF daughterboards are replaced by LFTX/LFRX cards [4]. For VLC transmitter and receiver front-ends, we use Hyperion Technologies LiFi R&D kit [5]. The physical layer of the demo system builds upon direct current biased optical OFDM (DCO-OFDM) and supports adaptive transmission with different modulation schemes/levels including BPSK, 4-QAM, 8-PSK, 16-QAM and 64-QAM. The feedback link employs a low-rate on-off keying (OOK) transmission scheme to send channel state information (in terms of SNR) to the OFDM transmitter. Consequently, the transmitter selects a modulation scheme which maximizes the spectral efficiency for the channel while satisfying a predetermined error performance requirement.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND DESCRIPTION

As illustrated in Figure 1, the main hardware components of the implementation consists of Ettus USRP x310 platforms [3] and Hyperion Technologies LiFi TX/RX frontends [5]. The Ettus USRP x310 is a software-defined radio platform which cover frequencies up to 6 GHz. Since it would be used for the implementation of a VLC system in our demo, we replaced the RF daughterboards with the low frequency transmitter/receiver (LFTX/LFRX) daughterboards [4] that support a frequency range of 0-30 MHz. The motherboard of the USRP X310s have 200 MHz analog to digital converter (ADC) and 800 MHz digital to analog converter (DAC). Incoming digital samples from the ADC and outgoing analog samples from the DAC are fixed at 200 MHz and 800 MHz respectively. The customizable FPGA has in-built blocks for sample rate conversion to and from the user requested sample rate. The USRP hard driver (UHD) blocks in LabVIEW are used to control transmit and receive operations of the USRP. In our demo, baseband communication and signal processing algorithms for signal generation, transmission and detection are implemented in LabVIEW.

Hyperion Technologies is a start-up company in Turkey that is developing LiFi R&D kits for rapid system prototyping. We employed their custom-designed LiFi TX/RX front-ends. The LiFi TX frontend has a powerful 5000K 186 lumen LED with an interchangeable lens mechanism whereas the LiFi RX frontend features a photodetector with 170° FOV enabling robust performance in non-line-of-sight channel conditions [5]. To

Fig. 1: (a) Block diagram of the transmitter/receiver (b) Demonstration set-up

Fig. 2: LabVIEW GUI interface of the OFDM RX and OOK TX

avoid signal clipping by the LED in the LiFi TX frontend, the output of the USRP with a dynamic range of $[-1V, 1V]$ is kept below 200 mVpp. This limits the optical transmit power of the signal. We use a 5° freeform lens at the LiFi TX and plano-convex lens with a focal length of 25.4 mm at the LiFi RX for the downlink to boost the transmitted OFDM signal strength. Similarly, we employ a 5° freeform lens at the LiFi TX for the uplink to increase the feedback signal strength.

For link adaptation, average SNR of the received OFDM frame is estimated and compared with a look-up-table (LUT)

containing different modulation levels/schemes i.e BPSK, 4-QAM, 8-PSK, 16-QAM and 64-QAM. For each modulation level, a proper SNR range is defined [6] for a targeted BER of 3.8×10^{-3} . The SNR ranges are represented by distinct binary codewords. The codeword corresponding to the estimated SNR is selected and modulated using OOK and then fed to USRP X310B. The output of USRP X310B is fed to LiFi TX and transmitted on the uplink to Station A. The signal is first received by LiFi RX which converts the optical intensity to electrical signal. It is then fed to USRP X310A for analog-

to-digital conversion. The output digital samples from USRP X310A are sent to Station A for detection by an OOK baseband receiver in LabVIEW. The detected binary codeword is compared with the LUT and the modulation level/scheme corresponding to the received binary codeword is selected for the next OFDM frame transmission.

III. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

In our demonstration, attendees will observe in real-time the transmission of OFDM with varying modulation schemes /levels in response to changes in the optical channel to maximize spectral efficiency and satisfy the predefined error performance target. Figure 2 shows the screenshot of the LabVIEW GUI interface featuring the physical layer system parameters, waveforms, SNR level, noise level and the received constellation.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We have demonstrated an adaptive OFDM LIFI system using Ettus USRP X310 complemented with Hyperion tech-

nologies LIFI TX/RX frontends. As a future work, we will leverage this implementation to study the performance of link adaptation in vehicular visible light communication in outdoor environment.

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